

Alimentary Management via Food Supplements for Young Children with Autism: A Review

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Abstract

The primary traits of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) consist of the inability to socialize, communicate and use imagination, and/or manifestations of stereotypical behavior. A disruption in the development of an autistic brain has been widely accepted in explaining the neurodevelopmental causes linked to ASD, but the association between the brain and the condition remains unclear. In this regard, a majority of young children with ASD have been observed to manifest gastrointestinal (GI) problems with a rise in intestinal permeability contributing to the pathogenesis of severity of ASD symptoms. According to Hsiao (2014), the GI abnormalities, given their reported prevalence and correlation with the severity of key ASD-related behavioral abnormalities and the development of autism-related endophenotypes (e.g., immune dysregulation, hyperserotonemia, and metabolic dysfunction) are of particular interest in this paper. This review discusses the GI pathologies seen in ASD individuals and the association of particular GI conditions with known deficiencies in vitamins and minerals. With emerging evidence for a gut-brain connection in ASD (van De Sande, van Buul, & Brouns, 2014), vitamins and minerals have been widely used in nutritional or dietary treatment for ASD.

Key Words: Autism, Mineral, Nutrition, Treatment, Vitamin

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is often defined in terms of the *triad of impairments* – the phrase was first coined by Lorna Gladys Wing (b.1928-d.2014) and her associate, Judith Gould, in their pioneering work on autism as the central plank of the construct of ASD (see Wing & Gould, 1979): (i) impaired communication, (ii) impaired social skills, and (iii) a restricted and repetitive way of being-in-the-world. Garcia (2021) has defined the triad of impairments more or less along the same line, i.e., (i) difficulty in communication or language, (ii) social and emotional deficits, and (iii) inflexibility in thought and imagination, to describe the difficulties that those with ASD encounter on a daily living routine. According to Cashin, Sci and Barker (2009), “[T]he actual triad of impairment is static and ubiquitous unlike the variable and fluctuating behavioral manifestation. The actual triad of impairment in autism is visual as opposed to linguistic processing, impaired abstraction, and lack of theory of mind. The actual triad is central to all diagnosis that together makes up the autism spectrum” (p. 189). The triad of impairment referred to at present in the autism-related literature is a behavioral triad. Cashin et al. (2009) have extended the triad of impairment model to the triad that

underlies the behavioral manifestation: The real triad of impairment.

With the publication of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5th Edition (DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013), the triad of impairments has been replaced with the dyad of impairments (see Figure 1), i.e., [A] impairment in social communication and interaction, and [B] restrictive and repetitive pattern of behavior, and taking into account [C] the challenging sensory issues (i.e., deficits or impairments in sensory processing, modulation and response, resulting in what is known as sensory integration disorder, also known as sensory processing disorder) in the diagnostic assessment of ASD. The sensory issues constitute as a collective symptom under the restricted/repetitive behavior category, and it can be either hyper- or hypo-reactivity to stimuli (e.g., lights, sounds, tastes, touch, etc.) or unusual interests in stimuli (e.g., staring at lights, spinning objects, etc.) (APA, 2013). In addition to the dyad of impairments, the DSM-5 (APA, 2013) has also included the following categories of symptoms mentioned in the Behavior Assessment System for Children-Third Edition (BASC-3; Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2015a): “C.

Symptoms must be present in the early developmental period (but may not become fully manifest until social demands exceed limited capacities or may be masked by learned strategies in later life). D. Symptoms cause clinically significant impairment in social, occupational, or other important areas of current functioning. E. These disturbances are not better explained by intellectual disability (intellectual developmental disorder) or global developmental delay. Intellectual disability and autism spectrum disorder frequently co-occur; to make comorbid diagnoses of autism spectrum

disorder and intellectual disability, social communication should be below that expected for general developmental level” (also see Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2015b: BASC-3 Autism Spectrum Disorder 299.00 (F84.0), pp. 1-2). A severity assessment scale (levels 1-3) based on level of support needed for daily function has also been included in the diagnostic manual. The three levels are: Level 1 – requiring support; Level 2 – requiring substantial support; and Level 3 – requiring very substantial support (also see Camulli & Goh, 2018, p. 188, for detail).

Figure 1. DSM-5 Diagnostic Criteria for ASD

Causes of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)

Being a heterogeneous condition, ASD is not autism per se but a wide range of varieties or subtypes and specific subtypes. The cause of ASD is not one but many. Nobody knows exactly what causes autism, whose term was first coined by Paul Eugen Bleuler (b.1857-d.1939) in his 1911 book on schizophrenia (Bleuler, 1911/1950). Bleuler (1911/1950) used autism to describe a signature characteristic of adults with what was then known as dementia praecox (a group of schizophrenias) – “a severe mental illness: a state of insulation from reality so complete that it excluded other human beings” (p. 63).

Much later in 1943, Leo Kanner (b.1894-d.1981) used the term early infantile autism to describe the condition. A year later, Han Asperger (b.1906-d.1980) published a paper on some atypical neurological disorder resembling autism, which was named Asperger Syndrome (Asperger, 1944) after him. Still very little was known about ASD until the last few decades when more research has been carried out to study the enigmatic condition. Even today, there is a great deal of ASD that remains unknown, despite recent studies that have identified dozens of genes associated with the condition by studying so-called de novo mutations, i.e., newly arising changes to the genome found in children but not their parents (Alvarez, 2018; also see An et al., 2018, for more detail). To date, most de novo mutations linked to ASD have been found in protein-coding genes, but there are also autism-associated mutations in non-coding regions of the genome that

have yet to be identified (Alvarez, 2018). This constitutes the *unknowable unknown* (a term borrowed from D’Souza & Renner, 2014) domain that requires “deep knowledge and specific focus of research *that* may limit *our* perspective” (words in italic are the authors’ addition; D’Souza & Renner, 2014, p. 39) in the vast field of autism research.

This unknowable unknown in the current knowledge of ASD has been termed as “biological dark matter” (BDM for short; see Ross, 2016, for detail) – an informal term to describe an unclassified or poorly understood genetic material, which, in turn, may refer to genetic material produced by unclassified microbes. The term BDM can also be extended to include an un-isolated microbe, whose existence can only be inferred from the genetic material that it produces. In fact, some of the genetic material may not come under the three existing domains of life: bacteria, archaea and eukaryote. Hence, there is a possibility of a fourth domain of life may yet to be discovered (Lopez, Halary, & Baptiste, 2015; Wu et al., 2011). However, the current tools that are used to investigate strongly interacting species and folded proteins are still not advanced enough to image, detect and understand the BDM and its working (Ross, 2016). This means better and more advanced investigative tools are urgently needed now and in the future.

Because the disorder is so complex and no two individuals with autism are exactly alike, there are

probably many causes for autism. It is also likely that there is not a single cause for autism, but rather that it results from a combination of causes. Researchers (e.g., Amaral, 2017; Jick & Kaye, 2003; Ratajczak, 2011) in the field of autism are still investigating a wide range of possible varied causes of or contributors to ASD. These causes include the following: genetic mutations (Gaugler et al., 2014; Pinto et al., 2010), epigenetic interference (from the environment) (Hallmayer et al., 2011; Landrigan, 2010), hormonal disturbance (Berbel, Navarro, & Román, 2014; Xie, 2021), gastrointestinal and/or metabolic dysfunctions (Frye et al., 2015; Madra, Ringel, & Margolis, 2020), nutritional and dietary deficiencies (Herndon et al., 2009; Levy et al., 2007), breakdown in neurological connections (Wass, 2011; Zikopoulos & Barbas, 2013), and anomalous brain development (Chia, Lim, & Lee, 2017; Courchesne, Redcay, & Kennedy, 2004), and the list can be endless with more new hypotheses being proposed each year.

The main focus of this paper lies in the nutritional and/or dietary deficiencies in young children with ASD. As young children (as well as adults) with ASD may display significant abnormal or impaired metabolic or biochemical processes, vitamins and/or minerals have been recommended and are most widely used nutritional or dietary treatment for ASD. As such, high doses of vitamin (e.g., Vitamin A, Vitamin B6, Vitamin B12, Vitamin C) and/or minerals (e.g., magnesium and zinc) as well as other food supplements (e.g., Omega-3 fatty acid, dimethylglycine or DMG for short) may have been used to correct for this condition.

Vitamins and Minerals for Autism Treatment

Vitamins and minerals are most widely used in nutritional or dietary treatment for children (as well as adults) with ASD (Adams, 2015; Adams & Holloway, 2004; Zhou et al., 2013). According to the curriculum of the Autism Case Training (ACT)¹ (see Hyman et al., 2020, for detail), both the vitamin/dietary supplements and exercise-based therapies have been applied in ASD treatment for children. In the former, a list of vitamins and minerals (i.e., food supplements) with respective precautionary notes (e.g., side effects due to overdose and toxicity) used in nutritional or dietary treatment for children with ASD are provided below (Farrell, Rappaport, Sell, & Tang, 2011):

Vitamins are organic substances (made by plants and/or animals) while minerals absorbed by plants or eaten by animals are inorganic elements that come from soil and water. To grow normally and stay healthy, young children as well as adults need both

- (1) Carnosine, Vitamin E and Zinc (Zn): These are given together for antioxidant activity and production of the inhibitory neurotransmitter GABA (Chez et al., 2002). However, an overdose could cause irritability and hyperactivity;
- (2) Dimethylglycine (DMG): It is based on the theoretical belief that DMG can help to decrease inflammation and increase immune function. More research is needed to show its efficacy (see Lin et al., 2016, for more detail);
- (3) Melatonin: It is given to help with sleep onset and maintenance (Melke et al., 2008; Rossignol & Frye, 2014). No precautionary note has been provided;
- (4) Omega-3 Fatty Acids: These are given to reduce blood pressure and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol level (Amminger et al., 2007). An overdose or interaction with other anti-coagulants could result in hemorrhage;
- (5) Probiotics: It is given to counteract gastrointestinal bacterial and fungal overgrowth in the alimentary canal or gut system (especially between the pylorus and the anus). More research needs to be done to show the benefits of probiotics to individuals with ASD (see Navarro, Liu & Rhoads, 2016, for detail);
- (6) Vitamin A (cod liver oil): It is given to improve immune function and vision (see Lai et al., 2021, for more detail). It could cause hepatotoxicity and increased intracranial pressure;
- (7) Vitamin B6 (pyridoxine) and Magnesium (Mg): The vitamin is given to help in neurotransmitter production with the supportive effect of Mg (Nye & Brice, 2005). There is a risk of Vitamin B6 toxicity causing peripheral neuropathy as well as Mg toxicity;
- (8) Vitamin B12 (cobalamin) and Folic Acid: It is given intramuscularly with oral Folic Acid (also known as Leucovorin) to counteract decreased plasma antioxidant concentrations (Al-Farsi et al., 2013; Moretti et al., 2005; Zhang et al., 2016). There is currently no mention of risk of Vitamin B12 toxicity; and
- (9) Vitamin C (ascorbic acid): It is given to decrease stereotypic behaviors often seen in individuals with ASD (Dolske et al., 1993). Vitamin C toxicity could cause nephrolithiasis and gastrointestinal upset.

vitamins and minerals. However, better absorption of vitamins and minerals often comes from plants. According to Arkopharma Laboratories (2021), “[P]lant-based vitamins and minerals are better assimilated by a living organism, e.g., up to 150% improvement in the assimilation of Vitamins B3 and

¹ This is a seven modular developmental-behavioral pediatrics curriculum – developed by the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) Council on Children with Disabilities Autism

Subcommittee serves to educate future healthcare providers on fundamental components of identifying, diagnosing, and managing ASD through real life scenarios.

B6! Vitamins and minerals derived from plants are associated with natural complexes called co-nutrients” (para. 2-3). However, not all nutrients can be found in plants. According to Ramirez (2020), there are those that are not plant-based, such as the following: Vitamin B12, Vitamin D3, creatine, carnosine, heme iron² (found in meats), DHA and taurine.

Selected vitamins (e.g., multivitamin and megavitamin therapies) and minerals as food supplements have been used in ASD treatment (Adams, 2015; Adams & Holloway, 2004; Zhou et al., 2013). Adams (2015) cited from Golnik and Ireland (2009) to argue that “among the most widely recommended medical interventions for autism, and are recommended by 49% of physicians for children with autism” (p. 2376) is the use of vitamin/mineral supplements. For the rest of this paper, the term *alimentary management* will be used in place of vitamin/mineral supplement in ASD treatment.

Many published studies (e.g., El-Ansary et al., 2017; Frustaci et al., 2012; James et al., 2004) have reported on biomarkers of increased oxidative stress in children with ASD. As vitamins and minerals are important anti-oxidants, Frustaci et al. (2012) suggested that children with ASD might have decreased levels of vitamins/minerals and/or increased need for them. Adams (2015) cited three studies (i.e., James et al., 2004, 2006, 2009) to show that children with ASD “have increased oxidative stress, impaired methylation (decreased S-Adenosyl methionine³ or SAM for short), and decreased glutathione, compared to neurotypical children ... and that certain vitamins and minerals can be helpful to them” (p. 2376).

In 2014, Professor James B. Adams of Arizona State University with his team founded the non-profit Autism Nutrition Research Center (ANRC) and came up with guidelines (see ANRC, 2020, for

updated detail) designed to provide optimal nutritional support for most children and adults with ASD. Known as the ANRC Essentials, it is a comprehensive multi-vitamin/mineral supplement containing over 30 ingredients, at doses that are determined to be optimal based on the ANRC research studies for individuals with ASD (see Adams, 2015, for detail). Special ingredients in the ANRC Essentials include the following (see Adams, 2015, p. 2377-2378): (i) Vitamins B1, B2, B3, B5, B6, B12, biotin, folate, C, D, and K, whose doses are relatively high (above the Recommended Dietary Allowances or RDA for short) but are thought to be important for children with autism; (ii) Folate as methyltetrahydrofolate (instead of folic acid as it is seen as unhelpful to children with ASD) (James et al., 2004); (iii) MSM (a good source of sulfate which is low in many individuals with ASD (Adams et al., 2011a); and (iv) Low-dose lithium (low in many children with ASD and their mothers), but the recommended quantity is about equivalent to typical RDA, and also far below the levels when prescribed as a psychiatric medication (Adams et al., 2011a).

Table 1 shows a list of selected vitamins (with ANRC-recommended dosages) that have been used in the alimentary management of ASD (with cited studies): Vitamins A (Lai et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2017), B1 (Lonsdale, 2004; Smart et al., 2019), B2 (Kałużna-Czaplińska, Socha, & Rynkowski, 2011), B3 (Melillo, 2016a; Willyard, 2021), B5 (Melillo, 2013, 2016b), B6 (Kałużna-Czaplińska, Socha, & Rynkowski, 2011; Martineau et al., 1985), B9 (Nuttall, 2017), B12 (Pineles, Avery, & Liu, 2010; Zhang, Yu, & Liu, 2018), C (McGinnis, 2004; Rafee, Burrell & Cederna-Meko, 2019), D3 (Cannell, 2017; Feng et al., 2017) and E (Daniells, 2009; Morris & Agin, 2009) ... in addition to several minerals such as calcium, choline, copper, iron, lithium, magnesium, manganese, potassium, selenium, and zinc, to name some of them here.

Table 1. Essential Roles of Selected Vitamins used in Alimentary Management of ASD

Vitamin	Chemical Structure	Essential Role
Vitamin A (Retinol) Recommended dosage: 8000 IU (ANRC, 2014) ⁴		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential for vision • Strengthening of immunity • Keeping skin & connective tissues healthy

² There are two types of iron: (i) heme iron is found in meats; and (ii) while non-heme iron is found in plant-based foods. “*Our bodies absorb heme iron at a higher rate compared to non-heme iron. If a person is a vegetarian (or vegan), s/he has to keep in mind that his/her body can only absorb 2-20% of non-heme iron. Heme iron from animal-based sources has a 15-35% absorption rate*” (words in italic are authors’ substitution; see Brennan, 2020, para. 10).

³ S-Adenosyl methionine (SAM), most of which is produced and consumed in the liver, is a common co-substrate involved in anabolic reactions (e.g., methyl group transfers, transsulfuration, and aminopropylation) that take place throughout the body.

⁴ Formulation of ANRC Essentials (2014) as cited in Table 2 (Adams, 2015, p. 2378).

Vitamin B1
(Thiamin)
Recommended dosage:
30mg (ANRC, 2014)

- Keeping nerves & muscle tissues healthy
- Processing of carbohydrates $(CH_2O)_n$ & some proteins

Vitamin B2
(Riboflavin)
Recommended dosage:
40mg (ANRC, 2014)

- Essential for body growth
- Production of erythrocytes
- Keeping the eyes healthy
- Processing of carbohydrates $(CH_2O)_n$

Vitamin B3
(Niacin: on the left -
Nicotinic Acid; & on
the right -
Nicotineamide)
Recommended dosage:
50mg (ANRC, 2014)

- Essential for digestion & keeps digestive system healthy
- Processing of carbohydrates $(CH_2O)_n$

Vitamin B5
(Pantothenic Acid)
Recommended dosage:
30mg (ANRC, 2014)

- Production of erythrocytes
- Processing of carbohydrates $(CH_2O)_n$
- Keeping the digestive system healthy

Vitamin B6
(Pyridoxal Phosphate)
Recommended dosage:
20mg (ANRC, 2014)

- Essential for making neurochemicals
- Essential for normal brain function
- Production of erythrocytes
- Production of granulocytes or immune system cells

Vitamin B9
(Folic Acid)
Recommended dosage:
not provided

- Essential for growing tissues
- Essential for brain function & mental health
- Production of DNA & RNA

Vitamin B12
(Cobalamin)
Recommended dosage:
600mcg (ANRC, 2014)

- Essential for health of nervous system
- Production of erythrocytes
- Production of DNA & RNA

Vitamin C
(Ascorbic Acid)
Recommended dosage:
500mg (ANRC, 2014)

- Essential for healthy immune system
- Production of collagen needed for making connective tissues
- Absorption of non-heme iron
- Wound healing
- Protective effects against many cancers

Vitamin D3
(Cholecalciferol)
Recommended dosage:
1500 IU

- Beneficial to mood, heart health & weight loss
- Absorption of calcium (Ca) & phosphorus (P)
- Strengthening of bones
- Keeping immune system healthy

Vitamin E
(Alpha-Tocopherol)
Recommended dosage:
100mg

- As an antioxidant to help prevention of damage to cells
- Production of erythrocytes
- Preventive role in cancer

According to Bjørklund et al. (2019), “[I]nsufficient intake of vitamins and minerals through poor food habit has been considered as one of the main contributing factors to numerous child health problems such as anemia, scurvy, hypothyroidism, rickets, and so on due to lack of iron, vitamin C, iodine, and Vitamin D, respectively” (p. 374). The same has been also observed in children with ASD, especially in vitamin deficiency, resulting in challenging issues – weak digestion capacity, poor absorption, abnormal or impaired metabolic or biochemical processes – such that high doses of vitamins B1, B2, B3, B5, B6, B12, C, and D become critical for children with ASD (Adams, 2015; Bjørklund et al., 2019) and are best included in their alimentary management. For instance, vitamins B2 and B6 are essential in helping to decrease dicarboxylic acids (HO₂C(CH₂)_nCO₂H) level in the

urine of children with ASD (Kałużna-Czaplińska, Socha, & Rynkowski, 2011). Duvall et al. (2013) also reported of a case of a child with severe ASD who displayed limp, tachypnea, cough, hypoxin and tachycardia-induced pulmonary hypertension due to inadequate levels of vitamins B1, B6, B12 and D, and also undetected Vitamin C level. In another instance, DeSoto (2016) hypothesized and reported the supportive role of Vitamin K in neural development as earlier studies (e.g., Adams et al., 2011b; Johnson et al., 2008) found that children with ASD frequently suffered from Vitamin K deficiency more than neurotypical children, and Hyman et al. (2012) recommended for inclusion of Vitamin K in nutrient supplement for children with ASD. Table 2 below provides a summary of selected studies supporting the inclusion of selected vitamins in the alimentary management for children with ASD.

Table 2. Selected Vitamin for Inclusion in Alimentary Management of ASD

Vitamins (Selected)	Studies supporting the inclusion of vitamins in the alimentary management for children with ASD
Vitamin A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in the oxytocin level via the CD38 process pathway⁵ in individuals with ASD (Riebold et al., 2011) leads to significant increase in brain activity and social abilities (Gordon et al., 2013)
Vitamin B1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves symptoms of children with ASD (Lonsdale, Shamberger & Audhya, 2002) • Essential in apoptotic factors, neurotransmitter system and oxidative stress; impacts positively on basic myelin protein glycogen synthetase kinase-3β, alpha-1 antitrypsin, and glyoxalase 1 (Khanh vinh quốc Lương & Lan Thi Hoàng Nguyễn, 2013)
Vitamin B2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supplementation of Vitamin B2 helps Vitamin B6 and magnesium to reduce excretion of urinary dicarboxylic acids in autistic children and increase excretion of carboxylic acids is related to excessive bacterial overgrowth, which has been related to ASD resulting in an impairment in the gut-brain axis (Gałtarek et al., 2020; Kałużna-Czaplińska, Socha, & Rynkowski, 2011)
Vitamin B3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vitamin B3 (niacin) is required in folate metabolism; abnormalities in folate metabolism have been linked to ASD (Frye, Slattery, & Quadros, 2017)
Vitamin B6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vitamin B6 and magnesium (with Vitamin B2 supplementation) help to reduce excretion of urinary dicarboxylic acids in autistic children, increase excretion of carboxylic acids related to excessive bacterial activity in the gut (called bacterial

⁵ “CD38 (cluster of differentiation 38) is encoded by the CD38 gene. It acts as an enzyme in several cellular reactions involved in calcium (Ca²⁺) mobilization and signaling” (Kelly, 2019, para. 7).

	overgrowth known to associate with ASD) which is an impairment in the gut-brain axis (Gałtarek et al., 2020; Kałużna-Czaplińska, Socha, & Rynkowski, 2011)
Vitamin B12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential for brain or cognitive development (Hendren et al., 2016; Morris et al., 2007) • Better management of depression and anger (Fraguas et al., 2006; Fava & Mischoulon, 2009)
Vitamin C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential for a healthy immune system which some children with ASD are suffering from due to Vitamin C deficiency (Rafee, Burrell, & Cederna-Meko, 2019) • Supplementation of Vitamin C contributes to a reduction in the stereotypical behaviors such as rocking, flapping hands, and pacing seen in children with ASD (Dolske et al., 1993), but further research is needed
Vitamin D3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential for neurodevelopment and gene regulation (Tovey, 2021) • Reduction in the risk of ASD (Saad et al., 2018) • Strengthening of strengthen bone and teeth formation in babies (Bowles, 2017)
Vitamin E	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential for combating inflammation and oxidative stress observed in children with ASD (Pangrazzi, Balasco, & Bozzi, 2020) • Combination of omega-3 fatty acids and vitamin E may improve speech in autistic children with verbal disorders (Morris & Agin, 2009) • Combination of omega-3 fatty acids and Vitamin E may improve behavior in children with neurodevelopmental disorders such as ASD (Gumprich & Rockway, 2014)
Vitamin K	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential for neural development in young children (Adams et al., 2011b; DeSoto, 2016); Hyman et al., 2012)

Besides vitamins, minerals (e.g., calcium, magnesium and zinc) have also been found to play an essential role in the alimentary management of children (as well as adults) with ASD (Babaknejad et al., 2016). According to Babaknejad et al. (2016), “[I]n comparison with healthy individuals, autistic patients, have different levels of trace elements like copper, magnesium, and zinc (Dufault et al., 2009; Morris & Agin, 2009)” (p. 2). A trace element (also known as minor element) is a chemical element whose concentration is very low (i.e., a trace amount) (Bhattacharya, Misra & Hussain, 2016). These elements can be placed under two categories; (i) essential and (ii) non-essential. It is the former that are required for important physiological and biochemical processes in both plants and animals. They “have been proven to influence the brain neurotransmitter metabolism significantly” (Babaknejad et al., 2016, p. 2). Not only do trace elements play a role in biological processes, they also function as catalysts engaging in oxidation and reduction mechanisms (see Wada, 2004, for detail).

According to the late Professor Bell Freedman (b.1950-d.2015) of Dalhousie University, Halifax, in Canada, “[T]race elements that are most often associated with environmental toxicity are the heavy metals cadmium, chromium, cobalt, copper, iron, lead, mercury, nickel, silver, tin, and zinc, as well as the lighter elements aluminum, arsenic, and selenium. Some cases of elemental pollution are natural in origin” (Freedman, 2018, p. 426). In fact, toxic elements (e.g., lead and mercury) and

deficiency of nutrients as well as trace elements are known as environmental factors that appear as “one cause of those epigenetic changes in wild and laboratory animals” (Leitch, 2021, para. 6) and Kelley et al. (2021, p.) have warned that humans are not immune to the effect of harmful environmental chemicals.

Among the several important trace elements in cell signaling, zinc (Zn) “plays a vital role in enzyme function, nucleic acid metabolism, growth, and finally cellular repair, most importantly in pregnant women and newborns” (Babaknejad et al., 2016, p. 2). Zn deficiency (especially when measuring Zn levels in the plasma, hair, and nails) has been found high in children diagnosed with ASD (Faber et al., 2009) and it constitutes a major factor in the etiology of behavioral and mood disturbances (Sayehmiri et al., 2015, p. 2). Zn also plays a role in immune system functioning (Prasad 1995), protein synthesis (Prasad 1995), wound healing (Heyneman 1996), DNA synthesis (IOM/FNB 2001), and cell division (Prasad 1995). In addition, according to Prasad et al. (1997), Zn is required for proper sense of taste (gustatory) and smell (olfactory), which can be determined via the administration of the Sensory Profile (Dunn, 1999).

Another important trace element is copper (Cu). Bjørklund (2013) reported that a disturbance in the copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn) metabolism is found in children with ASD in the following ways: (i) Zinc deficiency; (ii) excess Cu levels; and (iii) low Zn/Cu

ratio; these issues of Zn/Cu imbalance are common in children diagnosed with an ASD.

Given the importance of Zn/Cu metabolism for healthy neurological functioning and detoxification of heavy metals (including Hg), Faber et al. (2009) argued that these two trace elements may contribute in the pathogenesis of ASD.

Another essential trace mineral is iron (Fe) – a constituent of hemoglobin and myoglobin – that plays a vital role in the transport of oxygen (O₂) in the body. Iron deficiency (ID), with or without anaemia, can impair cognition and affect and is associated with developmental slowing in infants and mood changes and poor concentration in children with ASD (Latif, Heinz, & Cook, 2002). Although studies done on the association between ID parameters and clinical symptoms of ASD have been sporadic, high prevalence of iron deficiency (ID) and iron deficiency anemia (IDA) has been reported in children with ASD (Bilgiç et al., 2010; Dosman et al., 2006; Latif, Heinz, & Cook, 2002). However, a recent study done by Gunes, Ekinci and Celik (2017) found the hemoglobin levels of children with ASD were lower than neurotypical children and argued that it was not sufficient to result in anemia. They postulated that the IDA in children with ASD might be associated with intellectual disability instead of ASD symptom severity.

Selenium (Se), another trace mineral, is essential to good health. Se plays vital roles in DNA synthesis, thyroid hormone metabolism, reproduction, as well as protection from oxidative damage and infection (Ross et al., 2012). Its major dietary source can be found in plants, where its concentration generally reflects the concentration of the trace element in soils. However, some meats and seafood can also contribute dietary Se. Se is frequently used in the alimentary management of children with ASD, where the imbalance of Se is believed to cause the metabolic/psycho-metabolic disturbances. According to Skalny et al. (2018), “the mechanisms of the proposed Se neuroprotective effect in ASD may involve inhibition of oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and microglia activation. In addition, synaptic dysfunction and gut-brain axis disturbances might be modified” (p. 193). However, more studies are needed to understand and highlight the mechanisms of the potential neuroprotective effects of Se in ASD as well as its efficiency in clinical trials. The efficiency of Se used in alimentary management of ASD remains unclear. “Moreover, data on the role of Se metabolism in ASD are insufficient and contradictory” (Skalny et al., 2018, p. 193).

There are still many other minerals that are not discussed in this paper. Interested readers can always search in the Google Scholar for these papers on specific minerals, their key roles and how they can affect children with ASD.

Conclusion

Children with ASD are often reported by their caregivers to have food selectivity and restricted diets, putting them at risk for nutritional deficiencies (see Reynolds et al., 2012, for detail). Previous studies (e.g., Dosman et al., 2007; Herndon et al., 2009; Lindsay et al., 2006) have raised concerns about dietary insufficiency – in terms of the intake of iron, B vitamins, Vitamin D, vitamin K, calcium, and Zn – in one-third of children with ASD (Reynolds et al., 2012)

Food supplements or dietary nutrients – both vitamins and minerals – can induce epigenetic changes and these gradually “culminate in changes of the expression of genes through transcription and translation” (Bjørklund, 2013, p. 225). The interaction between food supplements/dietary nutrients and nuclear receptors can trigger the signaling pathway, leading to modulation of epigenetic change and gene expression. Different signaling pathways are attained by specific vitamin receptors for different vitamins and in turn affect gene expression. For instance, “Vitamin A serves as substrate for the biosynthesis of several retinoids that are essential for cell growth and cell differentiation as well as for vision” (Amann et al., 2011, p. 1405). Its signaling pathway is mediated by retinoid X receptor (RXR) heterodimerization with two orphan receptors: NGFI-B and NURR1⁶. The Vitamin A regulation of gene expression is a well-characterized illustration of direct nutrient regulation of gene expression, and McGrane (2007) explained that “[T]he downstream metabolites of retinol, all-trans and 9-cis retinoic acids are the bioactive components that bind and activate their cognate nuclear receptors to regulate target genes” (p. 497). It is not within the scope of this paper to delve into this complicated signaling process. Recently, Cheng et al. (2021) have found that deficiency in Vitamin A increases the risk of gastrointestinal comorbidity and exacerbates core symptoms in children with ASD.

However, there remains the ‘dark matter’ (unknowable unknown) of the human genome that has limited the current understanding of ASD. This is what the authors of this paper have come to the other side of the learning journey as they cross the bridge of exploration, in this example, on Vitamin A

⁶ Nurr1, whose antiapoptotic functions are vital for the development and survival of dopaminergic neurons, “is a member of the NGFI-B nuclear orphan receptor family which includes

two other members, Nur77 and Nor-1” (Zhang et al., 2009, p. 1408). However, the antiapoptotic mechanisms by which Nurr1 mediates these effects remain largely unknown.

and its effect on individuals with ASD. The food supplements will not be able to address the condition of ASD in its entirety. There are too many biological dark matter 'particles' in the present attempt to search for a probable solution using alimentary management via food supplements of the heterogeneous condition of ASD.

References

- Adams, J. B. (2015). Vitamin/mineral supplements for children and adults with autism. *Vitamins & Minerals*, 3(127), 2376-1318.
- Adams, J. B., Audhya, T., McDonough-Means, S., Rubin, R. A., Quig, D., Geis, E., ... & Lee, W. (2011a). Nutritional and metabolic status of children with autism vs. neurotypical children, and the association with autism severity. *Nutrition & Metabolism*, 8(1), 1-32.
- Adams, J. B., Audhya, T., McDonough-Means, S., Rubin, R. A., Quig, D., Geis, E., ... & Lee, W. (2011b). Effect of a vitamin/mineral supplement on children and adults with autism. *BMC Pediatrics*, 11(1), 1-30.
- Adams, J. B., & Holloway, C. (2004). Pilot study of a moderate dose multivitamin/mineral supplement for children with autistic spectrum disorder. *Journal of Alternative & Complementary Medicine*, 10(6), 1033-1039.
- Al-Farsi, Y. M., Waly, M. I., Deth, R. C., Al-Sharbaty, M. M., Al-Shafae, M., Al-Farsi, O., ... & Ouhtit, A. (2013). Low folate and vitamin B12 nourishment is common in Omani children with newly diagnosed autism. *Nutrition*, 29(3), 537-541.
- Alvarez, J. (2018, December 14). *Autism risk factors identified in? dark matter? of human genome*. Retrieved from: <https://psych.ucsf.edu/news/autism-risk-factors-identified-'dark-matter'-human-genome>.
- Amann, P. M., Eichmüller, S. B., Schmidt, J., & Bazhin, A. V. (2011). Regulation of gene expression by retinoids. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 18(9), 1405-12
- Amaral, D. G. (2017, January 31). Examining the causes of autism. In *Cerebrum: The Dana Forum on Brain Science*. Dana Foundation. Retrieved from: <https://dana.org/article/examining-the-causes-of-autism/>.
- Amminger, G. P., Berger, G. E., Schafer, M. R., Klier, C., Friedrich, M. H., & Feucht, M. (2007). Omega-3 fatty acids supplementation in children with autism: A double-blind randomized, placebo-controlled pilot study. *Biological Psychiatry*, 61(4), 551-553.
- An, J.-Y., Lin, K., Zhu, L., Werling, D. M., Dong, S., Brand, H., ... Sanders, S. J. (2018). Genome-wide de novo risk score implicates promoter variation in autism spectrum disorder. *Science*, 362(6420). Article ID: eaat6576.
- Arkopharma Laboratories (2021). *Why 100% plant-based vitamins and minerals?* Retrieved from: <https://www.arkopharma.com/en-SG/why-100-plant-based-vitamins-and-minerals>.
- Asperger, H. (1944). Die "Autistischen Psychopathen" im Kindesalter. *Archiv für Psychiatrie und Nervenkrankheiten*, 117, 76-136.
- Autism Nutrition Research Center (2020). *ANRC guidelines for comprehensive nutritional support*. Retrieved from: <https://www.autismnrc.org/assets/images/ANRC%20Product%20Images%202020/ANRC%20Guidelines%20-final%204-27-2020.pdf>.
- Babaknejad, N., Sayehmiri, F., Sayehmiri, K., Mohamadkhani, A., & Bahrami, S. (2016). The relationship between zinc levels and autism: Systematic Review and meta-analysis. *Iranian Journal of Child Neurology*, 10(4), 1-9.
- Berbel, P., Navarro, D., & Román, G. C. (2014). An evo-devo approach to thyroid hormones in cerebral and cerebellar cortical development: etiological implications for autism. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 5, 146.
- Bhattacharya, P. T., Misra, S. R., & Hussain, M. (2016). Nutritional aspects of essential trace elements in oral health and disease: An extensive review. *Scientifica*, 1-12. Article ID 5464373.
- Bilgiç, A., Gürkan, K., Türkoğlu, S., Akça, Ö. F., Kılıç, B. G., & Uslu, R. (2010). Iron deficiency in preschool children with autistic spectrum disorders. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 4(4), 639-644.
- Bjørklund, G. (2013). The role of zinc and copper in autism spectrum disorders. *Acta Neurobiol Exp (Wars)*, 73(2), 225-236.
- Bjørklund, G., Waly, M. I., Al-Farsi, Y., Saad, K., Dadar, M., Rahman, M. M., ... & Kałużna-Czaplińska, J. (2019). The role of vitamins in autism spectrum disorder: what do we know? *Journal of Molecular Neuroscience*, 67(3), 373-387.
- Bleuler, P. E. (1911/1950). *Dementia praecox or the group of schizophrenias* [translated by Joseph Zinkin, pp. 63-68]. New York, NY: International Universities Press.
- Bowles, J. T. (2017, April 13). *Autism: New studies show direct link to vitamin D3 deficiency*. Retrieved from: <https://jeffbowles.com/autism-vitamin-d3-deficiency-linked/#:~:text=Introduction%3A%20Folate%20is%20to%20spina%20bifida%20as%20Vitamins,help%20strengthen%20bone%20and%20teeth%20formation%20in%20babies>.
- Brennan, M. (2020, December 11). *Everything you need to know about heme iron*. Retrieved from: <https://www.activeiron.com/blog/everything-you-need-to-know-about-heme-iron/>.
- Camulli, J. E., & Goh, L. A. L. (2018). Re-conceptualizing autistic savantism as a spectrum

- syndromic disorder: A sequel to the case study of a young adult savant artist. *European Journal of Special Education Research*, 3(4), 185-204.
- Cannell, J. J. (2017). Vitamin D and autism, what's new? *Reviews in Endocrine and Metabolic Disorders*, 18(2), 183-193.
- Cashin, A., Sci, D. A., & Barker, P. (2009). The triad of impairment in autism revisited. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychiatric Nursing*, 22(4), 189-193.
- Cheng, B., Zhu, J., Yang, T., Guo, M., Lai, X., Li, Q., ... & Li, T. (2021). Vitamin A deficiency increases the risk of gastrointestinal comorbidity and exacerbates core symptoms in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Pediatric Research*, 89(1), 211-216.
- Chez, M. G., Buchanan, C. P., Kamen, J. L., & Becker, M. (2002). Double-blind, placebo-controlled study of L-carnosine supplementation in children with autistic spectrum disorders. *Journal of Child Neurology*, 17(11), 833-837.
- Chia, K.H., Lim, B.H., & Lee, B.M. (2017). Chapter 2: Neuroimaging studies on the autistic brain: Praxiological implications for educational therapists. In A. Cost & E. Villalba (Eds.), *Horizons in Neuroscience Research: Vol. 32* (pp. 79-128). Hauppauge, NY: Nova Science Publishers.
- Courchesne, E., Redcay, E., & Kennedy, D. P. (2004). The autistic brain: birth through adulthood. *Current Opinion in Neurology*, 17(4), 489-496.
- Daniells, S. (2009, August 20). *Omega-3, vitamin E mix shows potential for autistic speech*. Retrieved from: <https://www.nutraingredients.com/Article/2009/08/19/Omega-3-vitamin-E-mix-shows-potential-for-autistic-speech>
- DeSoto, M. C. (2016). Speculations on vitamin K, VKORC1 genotype and autism. *Medical Hypotheses*, 96, 30-33.
- D'Souza, S., & Renner, D. (2014). *Not knowing: The art of turning uncertainty into opportunity*. London, UK: LID Publishing Ltd.
- Dolske, M. C., Spollen, J., McKay, S., Lancashire, E., & Tolbert, L. (1993). Preliminary trial of ascorbic acid as supplemental therapy for autism. *Progress in Neuropsychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*, 17, 765-774.
- Dosman, C. F., Drmic, I. E., Brian, J. A., Senthilselvan, A., Harford, M., Smith, R., & Roberts, S. W. (2006). Ferritin as an indicator of suspected iron deficiency in children with autism spectrum disorder: prevalence of low serum ferritin concentration. *Developmental Medicine and Child Neurology*, 48(12), 1008-1009.
- Dosman, C. F., Brian, J. A., Drmic, I. E., Senthilselvan, A., Harford, M. M., Smith, R. W., ... & Roberts, S. W. (2007). Children with autism: effect of iron supplementation on sleep and ferritin. *Pediatric Neurology*, 36(3), 152-158.
- Dufault, R., Schnoll, R., Lukiw, W. J., LeBlanc, B., Cornett, C., Patrick, L., ... & Crider, R. (2009). Mercury exposure, nutritional deficiencies and metabolic disruptions may affect learning in children. *Behavioral and Brain Functions*, 5(1), 1-15.
- Dunn, W. (1999). *Sensory profile*. San Antonio, TX: Psychological Corporation.
- Duvall, M. G., Pikman, Y., Kantor, D. B., Ariagno, K., Summers, L., Sectish, T. C., & Mullen, M. P. (2013). Pulmonary hypertension associated with scurvy and vitamin deficiencies in an autistic child. *Pediatrics*, 132(6), e1699-e1703.
- El-Ansary, A., Björklund, G., Chirumbolo, S., & Alnakhli, O. M. (2017). Predictive value of selected biomarkers related to metabolism and oxidative stress in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Metabolic brain disease*, 32(4), 1209-1221.
- Faber, S., Zinn, G. M., Kern Ii, J. C., & Skip Kingston, H. M. (2009). The plasma zinc/serum copper ratio as a biomarker in children with autism spectrum disorders. *Biomarkers*, 14(3), 171-180.
- Farrell, T., Rappaport, L., Sell, N., & Tang, B. (2011). *Vitamin and exercise-based therapies*. Developed for the Autism Case Training: A Developmental-Behavioral Pediatrics Curriculum. Retrieved from: <https://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/actearly/autism/case-modules/pdf/treatments/Vitamin%20Dietary%20Supplements%20and%20Exercise-Based%20Therapies.pdf>
- Fava, M., & Mischoulon, D. (2009). Folate in depression: Efficacy, safety, differences in formulations, and clinical issues. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 70, 12-17.
- Feng, J., Shan, L., Du, L., Wang, B., Li, H., Wang, W., ... & Jia, F. (2017). Clinical improvement following vitamin D3 supplementation in autism spectrum disorder. *Nutritional Neuroscience*, 20(5), 284-290.
- Fraguas, R. Jr, Papakostas, G. I., Mischoulon, D., Bottiglieri, T., Alpert, J., & Fava, M. (2006). Anger attacks in major depressive disorder and serum levels of homocysteine. *Biological Psychiatry*, 60, 270-274.
- Freedman, B. (2018). *Environmental science (6th edition)*. Halifax, Canada: Simple Book Publishing.
- Frustaci, A., Neri, M., Cesario, A., Adams, J. B., Domenici, E., Dalla Bernardina, B., & Bonassi, S. (2012). Oxidative stress-related biomarkers in autism: systematic review and meta-analyses. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 52(10), 2128-2141.

- Frye, R. E., Rose, S., Slattery, J., & MacFabe, D. F. (2015). Gastrointestinal dysfunction in autism spectrum disorder: The role of the mitochondria and the enteric microbiome. *Microbial Ecology in Health and Disease*, 26(1), 274-283.
- Frye, R. E., Slattery, J. C., & Quadros, E. V. (2017). Folate metabolism abnormalities in autism: Potential biomarkers. *Biomarkers in Medicine*, 11(8), 687-699.
- Garcia, M. (2021, August 6). *What is the triad of impairments? (With pictures)*. Retrieved from: <https://www.infobloom.com/what-is-the-triad-of-impairments.htm>.
- Gątarek, P., Józwiak-Pruska, J., Bjørklund, G., Chirumbolo, S., & Kałużna-Czaplińska, J. (2020). Urinary carboxylic acids (UCAs) in subjects with autism spectrum disorder and their association with bacterial overgrowth. *Reviews in Analytical Chemistry*, 39(1), 78-87.
- Gaugler, T., Klei, L., Sanders, S. J., Bodea, C. A., Goldberg, A. P., Lee, A. B., ... & Buxbaum, J. D. (2014). Most genetic risk for autism resides with common variation. *Nature Genetics*, 46(8), 881-885.
- Golnik, A. E., & Ireland, M. (2009). Complementary alternative medicine for children with autism: A physician survey. *Journal of Autism & Developmental Disorders*, 39(7), 996-1005.
- Gordon, I., Vander Wyk, B. C., Bennett, R. H., Cordeaux, C., Lucas, M. V., Eilbott, J. A., ... & Pelphey, K. A. (2013). Oxytocin enhances brain function in children with autism. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 110, 20953-20958.
- Gumprich, E., & Rockway, S. (2014). Can ω -3 fatty acids and tocotrienol-rich vitamin E reduce symptoms of neurodevelopmental disorders? *Nutrition*, 30(7-8), 733-738.
- Gunes, S., Ekinci, O., & Celik, T. (2017). Iron deficiency parameters in autism spectrum disorder: clinical correlates and associated factors. *Italian Journal of Pediatrics*, 43(1), 1-6.
- Hallmayer, J., Cleveland, S., Torres, A., Phillips, J., Cohen, S. B., Torigoe, T., ... & Risch, N. (2011). Genetic heritability and shared environmental factors among twin pairs with autism. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 68(11), 1095-1102.
- Hendren, R. L., James, S. J., Widjaja, F., Lawton, B., Rosenblatt, A., & Bent, S. (2016). Randomized, placebo-controlled trial of methyl B12 for children with autism. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychopharmacology*, 26, 774-783.
- Herndon, A. C., DiGiuseppi, C., Johnson, S. L., Leiferman, J., & Reynolds, A. (2009). Does nutritional intake differ between children with autism spectrum disorders and children with typical development? *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 39(2), 212-222.
- Heyneman, C. A. (1996). Zinc deficiency and taste disorders. *Annals of Pharmacotherapy*, 30, 186-187.
- Hsiao, E. Y. (2014). Gastrointestinal issues in autism spectrum disorder. *Harvard Review of Psychiatry*, 22(2), 104-111.
- Hyman, S. L., Levy, S. E., Myers, S. M., & Council on Children with Disabilities, Section on Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics (2020). Identification, evaluation, and management of children with autism spectrum disorder. *Pediatrics*, 145(1). Article ID: e20193447.
- Hyman, S. L., Stewart, P. A., Schmidt, B., Lemcke, N., Foley, J. T., Peck, R., ... & Ng, P. K. (2012). Nutrient intake from food in children with autism. *Pediatrics*, 130(Supplement 2), S145-S153.
- IOM/FNB – Institute of Medicine, Food and Nutrition Board (2001). *Dietary reference intakes for vitamin A, vitamin K, arsenic, boron, chromium, copper, iodine, iron, manganese, molybdenum, nickel, silicon, vanadium, and zinc*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press.
- James, S. J., Cutler, P., Melnyk, S., Jernigan, S., Janak, L., Gaylor, D. W., & Neubrandner, J. A. (2004). Metabolic biomarkers of increased oxidative stress and impaired methylation capacity in children with autism. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 80(6), 1611-1617.
- James, S. J., Melnyk, S., Jernigan, S., Cleves, M. A., Halsted, C. H., Wong, D. H., ... & Gaylor, D. W. (2006). Metabolic endophenotype and related genotypes are associated with oxidative stress in children with autism. *American Journal of Medical Genetics Part B: Neuropsychiatric Genetics*, 141(8), 947-956.
- James, S. J., Melnyk, S., Fuchs, G., Reid, T., Jernigan, S., Pavliv, O., ... & Gaylor, D. W. (2009). Efficacy of methylcobalamin and folic acid treatment on glutathione redox status in children with autism. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 89(1), 425-430.
- Jick, H., & Kaye, J. A. (2003). Epidemiology and possible causes of autism. *Pharmacotherapy: The Journal of Human Pharmacology and Drug Therapy*, 23(12), 1524-1530.
- Johnson, C. R., Handen, B. L., Mayer-Costa, M., & Sacco, K. (2008). Eating habits and dietary status in young children with autism. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*, 20(5), 437-448.
- Kałużna-Czaplińska J, Socha E, & Rynkowski J. B (2011). Vitamin supplementation reduces excretion of urinary dicarboxylic acids in autistic children. *Nutrition Research*, 31(7):497-502
- Kanner, L. (1943). Autistic disturbances of affective contact. *Nervous Child*, 2(3), 217-250.
- Kelley, J. L., Tobler, M., Beck, D., Sadler-Riggelman, I., Corey R. Quackenbush, C. R., Rodriguez, L. A., & Skinner, M. K. (2021).

- Epigenetic inheritance of DNA methylation changes in fish living in hydrogen sulfide-rich springs. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America (PNAS)*, 118(26). Article ID: e2014929118.
- Kelly, G. (2019, May 21). *What is CD38? An exploration of NAD+ consumption uses and functions of CD38*. Retrieved from: <https://neurohacker.com/what-is-cd38-an-exploration-of-nad-consumption-uses-and-functions-of-cd38>.
- Lai, X., Zhang, Q., Zhu, J., Yang, T., Guo, M., Li, Q., ... & Li, T. Y. (2021). A weekly vitamin A supplementary program alleviates social impairment in Chinese children with autism spectrum disorders and vitamin A deficiency. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 75(7), 1118-1125.
- Landrigan, P. J. (2010). What causes autism? Exploring the environmental contribution. *Current Opinion in Pediatrics*, 22(2), 219-225.
- Latif, A., Heinz, P., & Cook, R. (2002). Iron deficiency in autism and Asperger syndrome. *Autism*, 6(1), 103-114.
- Leitch, C. (2021, June 17). *Fish adapted to toxins pass epigenetic changes onto offspring*. Retrieved from: <https://www.labroots.com/trending/genetics-and-genomics/20689/fish-adapted-toxins-pass-epigenetic-changes-onto-offspring#:~:text=This%20research%20confirms%20previous%20work%20that%20has%20indicated,the%20effect%20of%20harmful%20chemicals%20in%20the%20environment>.
- Levy, S. E., Souders, M. C., Ittenbach, R. F., Giarelli, E., Mulberg, A. E., & Pinto-Martin, J. A. (2007). Relationship of dietary intake to gastrointestinal symptoms in children with autistic spectrum disorders. *Biological Psychiatry*, 61(4), 492-497.
- Lin, J. C., Chan, M. H., Lee, M. Y., Chen, Y. C., & Chen, H. H. (2016). N, N-dimethylglycine differentially modulates psychotomimetic and antidepressant-like effects of ketamine in mice. *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*, 71, 7-13.
- Lindsay, R. L., Eugene Arnold, L., Aman, M. G., Vitiello, B., Posey, D. J., McDougle, C. J., ... & Bozzolo, D. (2006). Dietary status and impact of risperidone on nutritional balance in children with autism: a pilot study. *Journal of Intellectual and Developmental Disability*, 31(4), 204-209.
- Liu, J., Liu, X., Xiong, X. Q., Yang, T., Cui, T., Hou, N. L., ... Li, T. Y. (2017). Effects of vitamin A supplementation on gut microbiota in children with autism spectrum disorders: A pilot study. *BMC Microbiology*, 17. Article ID: 204.
- Lonsdale, D. (2004). Thiamine tetrahydrofurfuryl disulfide: A little known therapeutic agent. *Medical Science Monitor*, 10(9), RA199-RA203.
- Lonsdale, D., Shamberger, R. J., & Audhya, T. (2002). Treatment of autism spectrum children with thiamine tetrahydrofurfuryl disulfide: A pilot study. *Neuroendocrinology Letters*, 23(4), 303-308.
- Lopez, P., Halary, S., & Baptiste, E. (2015). Highly divergent ancient gene families in metagenomic samples are compatible with additional divisions of life. *Biology Direct*, 10(64). Article ID: PMC4624368.
- Madra, M., Ringel, R., & Margolis, K. G. (2020). Gastrointestinal issues and autism spectrum disorder. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, 29(3), 501-513.
- Martineau, J., Barthelemy, C., Garreau, B., & Lelord, G. (1985). Vitamin B6, magnesium, and combined B6-Mg: therapeutic effects in childhood autism. *Biological Psychiatry*, 20(5), 467-478.
- McGrane, M. M. (2007). Vitamin A regulation of gene expression: molecular mechanism of a prototype gene. *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*, 18(8), 497-508.
- McGinnis, W. R. (2004). Oxidative stress in autism. *Alternative Therapies in Health & Medicine*, 10(6), 22-36.
- Melillo, R. (2013). *Autism: The Scientific Truth about Preventing, Diagnosing, and Treating Autism Spectrum Disorders--and what Parents Can Do Now*. New York, NY: TarcherPerigee.
- Melillo, R. (2016a, June 21). *Nutrition for the brain: Niacin*. Retrieved from: <https://www.drrobertmelillo.com/nutrition-brain-niacin/>.
- Melillo, R. (2016b, August 3). *Nutrition for the brain: Pantothenic acid*. Retrieved from: <https://www.drrobertmelillo.com/nutrition-brain-pantothenic-acid/>.
- Melke, J., Botros, H. G., Chaste, P., Betancur, C., Nygren, G., Anckarsäter, H., ... & Bourgeron, T. (2008). Abnormal melatonin synthesis in autism spectrum disorders (ASD). *Molecular Psychiatry*, 13(1), 90-98.
- Moretti, P., Sahoo, T., Hyland, K., Bottiglieri, T., Peters, S., Del Gaudio, D., ... & Scaglia, F. (2005). Cerebral folate deficiency with developmental delay, autism, and response to folinic acid. *Neurology*, 64(6), 1088-1090.
- Morris, C. R., & Agin, M. C. (2009). Syndrome of allergy, apraxia, and malabsorption: characterization of a neurodevelopmental phenotype that responds to omega 3 and vitamin E supplementation. *Alternative Therapies in Health & Medicine*, 15(4), 34.
- Morris, M. S., Jacques, P. F., Rosenberg, I. H., & Selhub, J. (2007). Folate and vitamin B-12 status in relation to anemia, macrocytosis, and cognitive impairment in older Americans in the

- age of folic acid fortification. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 85, 193-200.
- Navarro, F., Liu, Y., & Rhoads, J. M. (2016). Can probiotics benefit children with autism spectrum disorders? *World Journal of Gastroenterology*, 22(46). Article ID: 10093.
- Nuttall, J. R. (2017). The plausibility of maternal toxicant exposure and nutritional status as contributing factors to the risk of autism spectrum disorders. *Nutritional Neuroscience*, 20(4), 209-218.
- Nye, C., & Brice, A. (2005). Combined vitamin B6-magnesium treatment in autism spectrum disorder. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 4. Article Number: CD003497.
- Pangrazzi, L., Balasco, L., & Bozzi, Y. (2020). Natural antioxidants: A novel therapeutic approach to autism spectrum disorders? *Antioxidants*, 9(12). Article ID: 1186.
- Pineles, S. L., Avery, R. A., & Liu, G. T. (2010). Vitamin B12 optic neuropathy in autism. *Pediatrics*, 126(4), e967-e970.
- Pinto, D., Pagnamenta, A. T., Klei, L., Anney, R., Merico, D., Regan, R., ... & Yaspán, B. L. (2010). Functional impact of global rare copy number variation in autism spectrum disorders. *Nature*, 466(7304), 368-372.
- Prasad, A. S. (1995). Zinc: An overview. *Nutrition*, 11(1 Suppl), 93-99.
- Prasad, A. S., Beck, F. W., Grabowski, S. M., Kaplan, J., & Mathog, R. H. (1997). Zinc deficiency: Changes in cytokine production and T-cell subpopulations in patients with head and neck cancer and in noncancer subjects. *Proceedings of the Association of the American Physicians*, 109, 68-77.
- Rafee, Y., Burrell, K., & Cederna-Meko, C. (2019). Lessons in early identification and treatment from a case of disabling vitamin C deficiency in a child with autism spectrum disorder. *The International Journal of Psychiatry in Medicine*, 54(1), 64-73.
- Ramirez, D. (2020, December 18). *Vegetarian health and nutrition: 7 Nutrients you can't get from plants*. Retrieved from: <https://veggie.news/2020-12-18-7-nutrients-you-cant-get-from-plants.html>.
- Ratajczak, H. V. (2011). Theoretical aspects of autism: Causes - A review. *Journal of Immunotoxicology*, 8(1), 68-79.
- Reynolds, A., Krebs, N. F., Stewart, P. A., Austin, H., Johnson, S. L., Withrow, N., ... & Hyman, S. L. (2012). Iron status in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Pediatrics*, 130(Supplement 2), S154-S159.
- Reynolds, C. R., & Kamphaus, R. W. (2015a). *Behavior assessment system for children—Third Edition (BASC-3)*. Bloomington, MN: Pearson.
- Reynolds, C. R., & Kamphaus, R. W. (2015b). *BASC-3: Autism spectrum disorder 299.00 (F84.0)* [Extracted from DSM-5 (APA, 2013)]. Bloomington, MN: Pearson.
- Riebold, M., Mankuta, D., Lerer, E., Israel, S., Zhong, S., Nemanov, L., ... Yaari, M. (2011). All-trans retinoic acid upregulates reduced CD38 transcription in lymphoblastoid cell lines from autism spectrum disorder. *Molecular Medicine*, 17, 799-806.
- Ross, A. C., Caballero, B., Cousins, R. J., Tucker, K. L., & Ziegler, T. R. (2012). *Modern nutrition in health and disease* (No. Ed. 11). Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Ross, J. L. (2016). The dark matter of biology. *Biophysical Journal*, 111, 909-916.
- Rossignol, A. D., & Frye, E. R. (2014). Melatonin in autism spectrum disorders. *Current Clinical Pharmacology*, 9(4), 326-334.
- Saad, K., Abdel-Rahman, A. A., Elserogy, Y. M., Al-Atram, A. A., El-Houfey, A. A., Othman, H. A., ... Abdel-Salam, A. M. (2018). Randomized controlled trial of vitamin D supplementation in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 59(1), 20-29.
- Sayehmiri, F., Babaknejad, N., Bahrami, S., Sayehmiri, K., Daarabi, M., & Rezaei-Tavirani, M. (2015). Zinc/calcium levels in the field of autism disorders: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Iranian Journal of Child Neurology*, 9(4), 1-9.
- Skalny, A. V., Skalnaya, M. G., Bjørklund, G., Gritsenko, V. A., Aaseth, J., & Tinkov, A. A. (2018). Selenium and autism spectrum disorder. In B. Michalke (ed.), *Selenium* (pp. 193-210). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Smart, A., Westmacott, K. L., Crew, A., Doran, O., & Hart, J. P. (2019). An Electrochemical Screen-Printed Amperometric Sensor for the Selective Measurement of Thiamine (Vitamin B1) in Food Supplements. *Biosensors*, 9(3). Article ID: 98.
- Tovey, A. (2021, August 5). New research suggests vitamin D benefits children with autism. Retrieved from: <https://www.autismparentingmagazine.com/vitamin-d-benefits-children-autism/>.
- Van De Sande, M. M., van Buul, V. J., & Brouns, F. J. (2014). Autism and nutrition: The role of the gut-brain axis. *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 27(2), 199-214.
- vinh quốc Lương, K., & Nguyễn, L. T. H. (2013). The beneficial role of vitamin D in obesity: Possible genetic and cell signaling mechanisms. *Nutrition Journal*, 12(1), 1-12.
- Wada, O. (2004). What are trace elements? Their deficiency and excess states. *Japan Medical Association Journal*, 47(8), 351-358.
- Wass, S. (2011). Distortions and disconnections: disrupted brain connectivity in autism. *Brain and Cognition*, 75(1), 18-28.

- Willyard, C. (2021). How gut microbes could drive brain disorders. *Nature*, *590*, 22-25.
- Wing, L., & Gould, J. (1979). Severe impairments of social interaction and associated abnormalities in children: Epidemiology and classification. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, *9*(1), 11-29.
- Wu, D., Wu, M., Halpern, A., Rusch, D. B., Yooseph, S., Frazier, M., Venter, J. C., & Eisen, J. A. (2011). Stalking the fourth domain in metagenomic data: Searching for, discovering, and interpreting novel, deep branches in marker gene phylogenetic trees. *PLOS ONE*, *6*(3). Article ID: e18011.
- Xie, G.H. (2021). Hypothalamic atrophy as a probable neuroprodrome to autism: A short review. *Journal of Early Years Research*, *1*(1), 1-9.
- Zhang, T., Wang, P., Ren, H., Fan, J., & Wang, G. (2009). NGFI-B nuclear orphan receptor Nurr1 interacts with p53 and suppresses its transcriptional activity. *Molecular Cancer Research*, *7*(8), 1408-1415.
- Zhang, Y., Hodgson, N. W., Trivedi, M. S., Abdolmaleky, H. M., Fournier, M., Cuenod, M., ... & Deth, R. C. (2016). Decreased brain levels of vitamin B12 in aging, autism and schizophrenia. *PloS One*, *11*(1). Article ID: e0146797.
- Zhang, Z., Yu, L., Li, S., & Liu, J. (2018). Association study of polymorphisms in genes relevant to vitamin B12 and folate metabolism with childhood autism spectrum disorder in a Han Chinese population. *Medical Science Monitor: International Medical Journal of Experimental and Clinical Research*, *24*, 370-376.
- Zikopoulos, B., & Barbas, H. (2013). Altered neural connectivity in excitatory and inhibitory cortical circuits in autism. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, *7*. Article ID: 609.
- Zhou, S. S., Zhou, Y. M., Li, D., & Ma, Q. (2013). Early infant exposure to excess multivitamin: a risk factor for autism? *Autism Research and Treatment*. Article ID: 963697.